

Additional file 1: Supplementary Figures

Fig S1. Granulocyte-colony stimulating factor and DMSO vehicle do not induce proliferation of Ewing sarcoma cell lines *in vitro*. (A-B) Ewing sarcoma cell lines and the low-passage cell culture DC-ES-6 were cultured in standard growth medium (10% serum) and treated for 72 h with (A) granulocyte-colony stimulating factor (GCSF) or (B) DMSO vehicle control. Relative cell numbers were measured by WST-1 colorimetric assay. Graphs represent mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of three independent experiments. Statistical significance was calculated for pairwise comparisons of relative cell number at maximum doses of GCSF or DMSO and respective non-treated control; none reached significance.

Fig S2. Serum-deprivation does not alter cell line groups of CXCR4-high and -low surface expressions. (A) Western blot analysis of total CXCR4 protein using an alternative (C-terminal) CXCR4 antibody reveals additional isoform bands. Whole cell lysates from Fig 3A were analyzed. Actin served as loading control. (B)-(C) Cells were grown to 70-80% confluence and starved in serum-free medium for 16 h before CXCR4 surface expression was analyzed by flow cytometry. LAN-5 neuroblastoma cells did not tolerate serum-free culture and were omitted from analysis; (B) depicts fractions of CXCR4-positive cells and (C) their relative fluorescence intensities (RFI; CXCR4 antibody relative to isotype control); asterisk (*) indicates significance of pairwise comparisons to corresponding culture in 10% serum (Fig 3).